

Fuelling the Distance: Improving Nutrition Practices in Ultra-Endurance Runners

Rationale, Aims and Objectives

Ultra-endurance running, also referred to as ultramarathon running or ultrarunning, involves events that exceed marathon distance or last for more than six hours. Events may span single or multiple days and often involve challenging environments and terrain. This places extreme demands on the body, making adequate nutrition critical for supporting performance, recovery, and long-term health. However, many athletes struggle to follow evidence-based nutrition practices. This research aimed to understand how ultra-endurance runners in Ireland make decisions about what, when, and how they eat and hydrate around training and competition. By exploring key factors influencing nutrition behaviours, including knowledge, environment, and motivation, this research identified practical gaps and areas where support is needed.

Research Findings

Qualitative data from ultra-endurance runners indicates that although they are generally aware of the importance of nutrition, this knowledge does not consistently translate into effective behaviours. Many athletes rely on instinct, trial-and-error, or advice from peers rather than qualified nutrition professionals. Time constraints, including work and family commitments, limit their ability to plan meals, often resulting in inconsistent fuelling. Fear of gastrointestinal (gut) issues strongly influences nutrition decisions, leading some to restrict or avoid certain foods based on personal experiences or anecdotal advice. Post-event, many athletes lack a structured approach to support optimal recovery.

Policy Implications

These findings highlight the need to move beyond simply providing nutrition information to these athletes. Policies and programmes should focus on understanding athletes' day-to-day realities to identify how best to apply knowledge in practical ways. Recommendations should be accessible, clear, and evidence-based, while allowing for individual tailoring. There is also a clear need to build trust and engagement with qualified nutrition professionals. Integrating expert guidance into athletic clubs and events could help to bridge the gap between science and practice, promoting safe and effective nutrition strategies and addressing misconceptions around gastrointestinal symptom management.

Industry Recommendations

Sporting organisations and industry stakeholders should provide practical tools for athletes, such as simple fuelling plans, nutrition checklists, and recovery guides. Nutrition education should be delivered through platforms that align with how athletes currently learn, namely through online platforms and peer networks. With regards to managing gastrointestinal symptoms, structured "gut training" can help athletes to build tolerance to foods during exercise, ultimately reducing fear-driven restrictive behaviours and negative performance impacts. Ensuring nutrition strategies are time-efficient and easy to integrate into daily life will be essential for improving adherence, performance, and long-term health outcomes in this growing population.

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Further Reading:

Ryan, T., Daly, E., & Ryan, L. (2026) Understanding the Behavioural Determinants of Nutrition Practices in Ultra-Endurance Runners in Ireland. *Sports*, 14(3), 109. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/sports14030109>

National Smart Specialisation Strategy (S3) Theme:

Life Sciences, Medtech & Medical Devices

Sustainable Development Goal (SDG):

SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being

Acknowledgement:

The author would like to sincerely thank their co-authors Dr Ed Daly and Dr Lisa Ryan from the Department of Sport, Exercise & Nutrition, ATU Galway.

The content and views included in this policy brief are based on independent, peer-reviewed research and do not necessarily reflect the position of RISE@ATU.

RISE@ATU is co-funded by the Government of Ireland and the European Union through the ERDF Northern & Western Regional Programme 2021-2027.

